

Table S1. Full Poisson regression incidence rate ratios (IRR) for injuries and lost workdays across all model specifications.

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Model label	Outcome	Factor	Level_vs_reference	Reference level	IRR	CI_95_lower	CI_95_upper	p value
Annual model (injuries)	Injuries	Program	2022–2025 vs 2021	2021	0.62	0.45	0.85	0.003
Annual model (lost workdays)	Lost workdays	Program	2022–2025 vs 2021	2021	0.52	0.47	0.57	<0.001
Department model	Injuries	Program	2022–2025 vs 2021	2021	0.6	0.43	0.82	0.001
Department model	Injuries	Department	Machining	Foundry	0.66	0.43	1.02	0.059
Department model	Injuries	Department	Support	Foundry	0.21	0.13	0.31	<0.001
Seniority model	Injuries	Program	2022–2025 vs 2021	2021	0.71	0.54	0.92	0.01
Seniority model	Injuries	Seniority	0–3 years	3–5 years	1.66	0.92	3.01	0.088
Seniority model	Injuries	Seniority	≥5 years	3–5 years	0.52	0.28	0.99	0.047
Age×seniority contrast	Injuries	Program	2022–2025 vs 2021	2021	0.7	0.54	0.91	0.007
Age×seniority contrast	Injuries	Age×seniority contrast	<30 & 0–3 years	≥36 & ≥5 years	4.42	2.85	6.84	<0.001
Education model	Injuries	Program	2022–2025 vs 2021	2021	0.66	0.51	0.86	0.002
Education model	Injuries	Education	Vocational college	General high school	0.43	0.21	0.89	0.023
Education model	Injuries	Education	Technical/vocational HS	General high school	0.71	0.43	1.18	0.188
Shift model	Injuries	Shift	16:00–00:00	08:00–16:00	0.63	0.52	0.77	2.10E-06
Shift model	Injuries	Shift	00:00–08:00	08:00–16:00	0.43	0.33	0.57	8.77E-10

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